

1 **CRISPR/Cas9 Genome Editing-Based Preclinical Theranostics, Biomarkers**
2 **and Drug Delivery Systems for Cancer Applications**

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1 **Abstract**

2 Cancer development is driven by diverse genetic aberrations, underscoring the
3 importance of innovative approaches like gene therapy for effective treatment. The
4 CRISPR/Cas9 gene-editing system has all the makings of a game-changing technique for future
5 disease treatment, owing to its pinpoint accuracy and efficiency in deleting disease-causing
6 genes or correcting damaging base mutations. A number of efficient Cas9 variants and
7 derivatives were recently designed to tackle the intricate genomic modifications that
8 accompany illnesses. In addition, CRISPR/Cas9 based systems are increasingly explored for
9 biomarker sensing and cancer diagnostics. Early identification, real-time monitoring, and
10 therapy stratification are made possible by CRISPR-driven biosensors, which can detect
11 circulating tumour DNA, microRNAs, or exosomal RNA with high specificity and sensitivity.
12 Furthermore, a variety of stimuli-responsive delivery strategies, including chemical and
13 peptide-assisted systems, light-activated mechanisms, glutathione-sensitive carriers, and pH-
14 responsive platforms, have been explored to improve intracellular release efficiency thereby
15 enhancing the precision of CRISPR/Cas9-mediated gene editing in cancer therapy. The
16 CRISPR/Cas9-enabled theranostic platforms employ engineered nanocarriers to
17 simultaneously deliver gene-editing tools and imaging agents, thereby facilitating
18 synchronized treatment monitoring and improved therapeutic precision. This review
19 emphasizes the transformative potential of CRISPR/Cas9-integrated theranostics, which
20 combine targeted gene editing with advanced imaging for enhanced therapeutic monitoring and
21 efficacy in cancer treatment.

22
23 **Keywords:** CRISPR/Cas9, biomarker, drug delivery system, theranostics, cancer, gene editing

1 1. Introduction

2 The clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats (CRISPR) and CRISPR-
3 associated (Cas) protein (CRISPR/Cas) system is a heritable adaptive immunological
4 mechanism seen in both archaeal and bacterial entities [1]. It is categorically divided into two
5 principal classes, comprising six kinds and numerous subtypes. In this system, class I employs
6 many effector proteins, whereas class II utilizes a singular effector protein for target
7 interference. The type II, class II CRISPR system, which utilizes a singular Cas9 protein, is
8 among the most extensively characterized and frequently employed systems within the
9 CRISPR/Cas family [2]. With the help of a fusion of trans-activating crRNA (tracrRNA) and
10 CRISPR-targeting RNA (crRNA), a molecule called single-guide RNA (sgRNA) binds to the
11 target DNA sequence, inducing double-stranded breaks (DSBs) upstream to the end of
12 the target sequence must be a "NGG" protospacer adjacent motif (PAM) for precise and highly
13 specific DNA cleavage to occur. Non-homologous end joining (NHEJ) and homology-directed
14 repair (HDR) are the two main DNA repair pathways that cells use to fix DSBs. NHEJ is a
15 flawed mechanism that causes insertions or deletions, leading to gene disruption by altering
16 the reading frame [4]. Conversely, HDR can facilitate specific DNA modifications with a DNA
17 template with homologous arms. Owing to the system's simplicity, the flexibility in PAM
18 requirements that facilitates the targeting of diverse DNA regions, and the high accuracy in
19 genome editing, CRISPR/Cas9 has been extensively embraced as the preferred instrument for
20 gene editing [5]. In cancer research, this is especially pertinent, as CRISPR has significantly
21 influenced our comprehension of cancer biology and several stages of cancer pharmacotherapy
22 development. The effective and rapid genome editing has helped identify rare gene mutations
23 specific to cancer, accelerated the process of finding and validating potential therapeutic
24 targets, enhanced disease modeling, and contributed to the development of new cancer
25 treatments [6].

26 Efficient delivery of the Cas9 protein and sgRNA to the nucleus is crucial for achieving
27 correct gene editing. A number of issues have impeded the investigation of physical and viral
28 delivery systems, including inefficiency, immunogenicity, inadequate packaging capacity, and
29 off-target effects. Despite the remarkable efficacy of CRISPR/Cas9, numerous biological
30 obstacles remain, with one of the most critical being the effective delivery of the CRISPR
31 machinery to the target cells or tissues [7]. In actuality, identifying an optimal carrier for
32 targeted delivery has presented a significant obstacle in accomplishing precise editing. To date,
33 various strategies have been employed; among these, the physical methods of electroporation
34 and microinjection for Cas9 administration have demonstrated limited success because

1 of reduced cell survival, hence constraining their application in vivo [8]. Viral vectors,
2 including lentivirus (LV), adenovirus (AV), and adeno-associated virus (AAV), can effectively
3 deliver the CRISPR/Cas9 system; nevertheless, issues such as mutagenesis, carcinogenesis,
4 and immunogenicity hinder its application. To fully harness the therapeutic potential of
5 CRISPR/Cas9, advancements in nanotechnology, particularly in delivery methods, can be
6 extremely beneficial [9]. Nanotechnology and nanovectors (non-viral vectors) have
7 significantly transformed the domain of medical sciences. Their numerous advantages,
8 including biocompatibility, site-specific controlled release, and enhanced encapsulation
9 efficiency, have established these nanovectors as optimal delivery vehicles for CRISPR/Cas9
10 applications [10]. Therefore, it is essential to understand the advantages and limitations of each
11 delivery strategy to select the most suitable method for cancer treatment.

12 CRISPR/Cas9 technologies have rapidly become adaptable instruments for both gene
13 editing and the prompt, precise identification of cancer biomarkers. In precision oncology, the
14 identification of biomarkers is crucial for predicting therapy response, monitoring disease
15 progression, and directing tailored treatment [11]. CRISPR-based functional genomic screens
16 facilitate the high-throughput identification of critical oncogenes, tumor suppressors, and genes
17 associated with drug resistance mechanisms. These insights substantially enhance the
18 comprehension of cancer heterogeneity and guide combinatorial treatment approaches.
19 Furthermore, CRISPR-based detection systems such as SHERLOCK and DETECTR, have
20 been developed to detect specific nucleic acid sequences such as DNA mutations and
21 circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA), with exceptional sensitivity and specificity [12]. These
22 devices exploit the collateral cleavage activity of Cas12 and Cas13 enzymes to provide
23 detectable signals upon target recognition, facilitating real-time, point-of-care cancer
24 diagnosis. Applications encompass the identification of single-nucleotide polymorphisms
25 and somatic mutations in oncogenes (e.g., KRAS, EGFR, TP53) as well as the non-invasive
26 surveillance of ctDNA via liquid biopsies [13]. The use of CRISPR/Cas-based technologies
27 in cancer theranostics presents significant potential for early diagnosis, treatment assessment,
28 and addressing resistance in both preclinical and clinical settings.

29 Modern advances in gene-editing technologies have positioned CRISPR/Cas9 systems at
30 the forefront of next-generation cancer therapies. The efficacy of CRISPR-based therapies
31 depends on the development of safe, efficient, and tumor-specific delivery mechanisms [14].
32 Recently, the emergence of nanomedicine appears to be a viable solution to the problems
33 associated with the CRISPR/Cas9 delivery system [15]. A significant amount of research on
34 nanomedicine has been undertaken about its potential applications in multifaceted cancer

1 detection and therapy, due to the favourable biocompatibility and payload capacity of
2 nanomedicine. An increasing number of scientists are encapsulating CRISPR/Cas9 within
3 nanoparticles to ensure its safe and efficient delivery [16]. Nanotechnology presents a feasible
4 solution to this problem by employing nanoscale materials that possess distinctive
5 physicochemical properties, facilitating the effective encapsulation and protection of
6 CRISPR/Cas9 components, thus enhancing their targeted delivery and cellular absorption [17].

7 Extracellular vesicles (EVs), including exosomes and microvesicles, have demonstrated
8 significant potential as natural, biocompatible carriers for the delivery of CRISPR payloads.
9 Engineered EVs can incorporate several CRISPR components, including plasmid DNA
10 (pDNA), messenger RNA (mRNA), ribonucleoproteins (RNPs), and Cas9/mRNA complexes,
11 via methods such as electroporation, co-incubation, or membrane fusion [18]. These
12 technologies provide a less immunogenic and precisely targeted approach for genome editing
13 in tumor cells. In addition to EVs, several synthetic nanocarriers such as lipid nanoparticles,
14 polymeric systems, and inorganic nanomaterials have been engineered to enhance the transport
15 efficiency, endosomal escape, and intracellular trafficking of CRISPR/Cas9 agents in cancer
16 treatment [19]. These systems are frequently modified with ligands or antibodies to improve
17 tumour selectivity and reduce off-target effects. The incorporation of imaging modalities into
18 CRISPR-loaded nanoplateforms has facilitated real-time observation of delivery,
19 biodistribution, and editing efficacy [20]. Techniques, including fluorescence imaging, MRI,
20 and photoacoustic imaging, are utilized to non-invasively assess CRISPR activity, providing
21 critical insights for dose optimization and therapy customization. The integration of
22 advanced EV-mediated and nanomaterial-based delivery with diagnostic imaging is
23 expanding the application of CRISPR/Cas9 technologies in precision cancer therapies [21].
24 This review explores the utilization of cancer biomarkers in combination with CRISPR/Cas9
25 gene editing and advanced imaging techniques, offering a powerful approach for precise cancer
26 gene targeting and real-time monitoring of therapeutic responses.

27 28 **2. Historical Background of CRISPR/Cas9 Technology**

29 One of the most ground-breaking scientific breakthroughs of the last several decades, the
30 CRISPR/Cas9 system has made previously unimaginable levels of accuracy and dependability
31 in genome editing possible [22]. Identified in 1987 as a naturally occurring immune defence
32 mechanism in *E. coli*, CRISPR was formally named in 2002 [23]. Its capacity to target nucleic
33 acids, along with its programmability, sequence specificity, high fidelity/sensitivity, and single-
34 base resolution, are among its many remarkable properties as a nucleic acid detection device.

1 This opens the door to the possibility of tailoring detection for various cancer kinds or
2 mutations unique to individual patients by allowing CRISPR-based detection systems to be
3 trained to target specific genomic sequences [24]. In addition, the remarkable properties of
4 CRISPR technology, such as its high sensitivity, specificity, speed, rapid deployability, and
5 cost-effectiveness, have made it a game-changing tool for molecular diagnostics and nucleic
6 acid analysis [25]. Several years ago, it was employed to identify nucleic acid-based cancer
7 biomarkers (NABCBs) [26]. Subsequent advancements, improvements in Cas9-based tumour
8 models, and the finding of trans-cleavage of Cas12/13 between 2015 and 2018 made it possible
9 to directly detect the RNA and DNA biomarkers linked with cancer [27]. There was great hope
10 that by 2020, CRISPR technology would be used to detect exosome RNA, ctDNA, and other
11 cancer biomarkers, showing great potential in cancer liquid biopsy [28]. CRISPR-based
12 technology is now being integrated with electrochemistry, microfluidics, colorimetry, and
13 fluorescence [29]. Since its beginning in 1974, nanotechnology has experienced notable
14 progress. The scanning tunnelling microscope (STM) was a game-changer for microstructure
15 study when it was introduced in 1981, and it accelerated the development of nanotechnology.
16 A new era in nano-material research began when graphene, which is made of pure carbon
17 nanotubes, was successfully created. With these findings, a bright era of comprehensive
18 experimental research into cancer diagnostics began. Currently, nanotechnology based in vitro
19 diagnostics are being extensively explored [30]. The detection process involves various
20 important steps, including signal generation, amplification, conversion, and collection, and it
21 has the potential to be a flexible and efficient model for biochemical analyses. Additionally, it
22 has demonstrated significant benefits in the detection of trace NABCBs, which in turn
23 encourages technological advancement and enhances detection speed, specificity, and
24 sensitivity [31]. Nanomaterials are useful for surface modification and signal amplification
25 because of their unique quantum size effect. Furthermore, nanomaterials can be modified and
26 functionalized using aptamers and oligonucleotides to enable the selective capture of specific
27 DNA or RNA sequences [32]. The incorporation of nanoparticles into microfluidic chips and
28 portable detection devices is a major step forward in the advancement of POCT detection. It
29 significantly reduces detection times, owing to its diminutive size. **Fig. 1** illustrates how nano-
30 biosensing systems can utilize the CRISPR/Cas system to identify specific nucleic acid
31 sequences using concentrated NABCBs [27].

1
 2 **Fig 1.** Characteristics of pertinent biomarkers at various stages of cancer progression and
 3 the historical application of CRISPR/Cas9 nanotechnology-based biosensing for the early
 4 identification of nucleic acid-based cancer biomarkers (NABCBs) [27]. Copyright 2025.
 5 Adapted from Springer Nature.

6
 7 **3. CRISPR/Cas9 Systems for Rapid and Sensitive Biomarker Detection**

8 The possibility of activity-based synthetic biomarkers to reach the sensitivity (limit of
 9 detection) required for early detection has been demonstrated in several preclinical
 10 investigations (**Fig. 2**) [33]. Synthetic biomarkers are utilized by enzyme-, small-molecule-,
 11 DNA, mammalian cell-, and bacterial cell-based sensors to enhance early cancer diagnosis
 12 [33]. Current clinical thresholds ($\sim 1 \text{ cm}^3$) are lowered by these methods, which employ various
 13 amplification techniques and tactics to enhance signal specificity [34].

1
2 **Fig 2. (I)** Synthetic biomarkers encoded genetically use signals specific to tumors to become
3 detectable; **(II)** Biomarkers for the detection of cancer at an early stage [33]. Copyright 2021.
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1 3.1. Biomarker identification for cancer treatment

2 The identification of biomarkers in cancer therapy has emerged as a cornerstone of
3 precision oncology, enabling clinicians to tailor treatments based on the unique molecular
4 characteristics of individual tumours [35]. Biomarkers, biological molecules that indicate
5 normal or abnormal processes, can provide critical insights into cancer diagnosis, prognosis,
6 and therapeutic response. Advances in genomic, transcriptomic, proteomic, and metabolomic
7 technologies have revolutionized the discovery and validation of such markers [36]. Examples
8 include gene mutations like *BRCA1/2*, overexpressed proteins like HER2, and epigenetic
9 alterations such as *MGMT* promoter methylation serve as valuable tools for guiding treatment
10 decisions. Moreover, non-invasive approaches like liquid biopsy allow real-time monitoring of
11 disease progression and therapeutic effectiveness [37]. The integration of biomarker research
12 into clinical oncology not only enhances treatment efficacy but also reduces unnecessary
13 toxicity, moving cancer care toward a more individualized and effective approach. One notable
14 use of CRISPR-Cas9 screening is the identification of treatment-sensitive groups through the
15 search for biomarkers [38].

16 Wang et al., developed core shell delivery of CRISPR/Cas9 and hydrophobic drugs
17 for breast cancer. This work presents a core shell nanoparticle (NP) called nDOX-
18 PL/pFBXO44 that is designed to deliver doxorubicin (DOX) and FBXO44-targeted
19 CRISPR/Cas9 plasmids (pFBXO44) simultaneously. The goal is to reprogramme cancer stem
20 cells (CSCs) and administer chemotherapy to tumour cells. The NPs have several interesting
21 properties, such as targeting tumour cells, escaping endosomes, and reducing responsiveness
22 to released DOX and plasmids in the cytoplasm. Combining CRISPR/Cas9-mediated
23 downregulation of FBXO44 expression with chemotherapy has the potential to transform CSC
24 into normal tumour cells, effectively suppress tumour development, and avoid noticeable
25 adverse effects in vivo (**Fig. 3**) [39].

Fig 3. A) Process flow diagram for the production of nDOX-PL/pFBXO44. (B) Diagram depicting the procedure for administering nDOX-PL/pFBXO44 following a tail vein injection, as well as the mechanism of action for treating triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) [39]. Copyright 2025. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

3.2. Genomic Identification of Key Genes Involved in Drug Resistance Mechanisms

The CRISPR/Cas9 technology has completely changed the way cancer treatments target drug resistance genes. By enabling precise, high-throughput gene knockout or activation screens, CRISPR/Cas9 allows researchers to systematically investigate the functional role of individual genes in response to anticancer drugs [40]. This approach has been widely used to uncover resistance mechanisms to targeted therapies, chemotherapy, and immunotherapy. For instance, CRISPR-based loss-of-function screens have identified key resistance-associated genes such as *TP53*, *PTEN*, *ABCBI*, and *NF1* in various cancer types [41]. Similarly, activation screens can reveal genes whose upregulation contributes to therapeutic resistance. These insights not only help in understanding the biology of drug resistance but also in discovering novel therapeutic targets to overcome treatment failure. The versatility and precision of CRISPR/Cas9 continue to make it an indispensable tool in the development of next-generation cancer therapies [14]. Recurrence of tumours, considered as one of the major challenges in

1 cancer treatment, is often related to the outcome of medication resistance that develops during
2 pharmacological therapy. Thus, essential techniques to address medication resistance include
3 discovering combination regimens and elucidating the resistance mechanism. Researchers have
4 been employing CRISPR/Cas9 technology to conduct large-scale screenings to identify critical
5 genes responsible for drug resistance or synergistic lethality [42]. MacLeod et al. discovered
6 the pathways that are responsible for the growth of glioblastoma (GBM) [43]. Specifically,
7 they highlight protein ubiquitination, SOCS3 and USP8 members of the SOX transcription
8 factor family, and DOT1L as crucial for GSC development. Furthermore, they uncover
9 temozolomide resistance pathways that may pave the way for combination approaches [43].
10 Through the utilisation of a genome-wide functional approach, which goes beyond static
11 genome analysis of bulk tumours, they uncover genetic dependencies in several biological
12 processes. This leads to a better comprehension of GBM development and treatment resistance
13 [43].

15 3.3. Nucleic acid detection

16 3.3.1. DNA mutation detection

17 Mutations in DNA have long been thought to be cancer's underlying cause and a source
18 of potential diagnostic and treatment targets [44]. Breast cancer susceptibility genes 1 and 2
19 (BRCA1 and BRCA2) are examples of altered genes that are invariably linked to a certain type
20 of cancer [45]. The CRISPR-Cas system's single-based identification and cleavage capacity
21 might make the detection of aberrant DNAs easier and more precise than the complicated
22 traditional ways of constructing electroanalytical platforms. It is possible to fine-tune the
23 CRISPR-Cas system such that it can identify and attach to certain DNA sequences down to the
24 base level. This makes it a strong contender for finding BRCA1 and BRCA2 point mutations
25 or tiny insertions/deletions [45]. In diagnostic tests, its capacity to cleave certain sequences can
26 be used to amplify signals. For example; **Fig. S1** demonstrates potential therapeutic clustered
27 regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats (CRISPR)-mediated targeting strategies for
28 cancer gene therapy [46]. In addition, diagnostic tools that combine CRISPR-Cas with
29 biosensor technology or electroanalytical platforms have the potential to outperform traditional
30 methods in terms of sensitivity, specificity, speed, and ease of use [47]. Moreover, personalised
31 risk assessment, early intervention, and enhanced early cancer diagnosis might all be possible
32 with the use of CRISPR-based detection tools. Especially for those who are genetically prone
33 to cancer, these developments may eventually lead to a change in thinking about cancer
34 treatment from a reactive to a proactive one [47].

1 Song et al., developed a DNA detection technique using CRISPR/Cas9 technology, that
2 eliminates the need for DNA elution steps [48]. This method utilises a DNA-capturing
3 (pDMAMS)-coated tube in conjunction with a CLAT assay. The pDMAMS-coated tube is
4 coated with lysis buffer and sample solution. The DNA is trapped on the surface by electrostatic
5 contact and then identified immediately by the CLAT test. Due to the CRISPR/Cas9 system's
6 specialised DNA recognition capabilities, DNA acquired on the pDMAMS-coated tube may be
7 directly detected. Detecting DNA in a single tube using the CLAT assay and a pDMAMS-
8 coated tube eliminates the need for complex extraction processes and improves sensitivity.
9 Further evidence of this method's practical utility came from studies conducted on animals
10 carrying tumours as depicted in **Fig. S2** [48].

11 12 3.3.2. Circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA) detection

13 Tumour cells or apoptotic tumour cells release fragments of cell-free DNA (cfDNA)
14 into the circulation, which is known as circulating tumour DNA (ctDNA). Although most
15 current methods are more costly and require long reporting periods, ctDNA offers a superior
16 prediction of early disease recurrence or metastatic illness in a number of malignancies
17 compared to conventional protein-based indicators [49]. A groundbreaking label-free approach
18 for detecting ctDNA based on the CRISPR-Cas system was revealed in 2020. The PIK3CA
19 exon 9 mutation was discovered with high sensitivity using electrochemical impedance
20 spectroscopy (EIS) [50].

21 An innovative 3D GR/AuPtPd nanoflower sensing device for efficient detection of
22 ctDNA has been developed by Chen et al., utilising the CRISPR/Cas9 cleavage-triggered
23 ESDR. Due to the complex operating processes and strict reaction conditions required for
24 ESDR amplification, this approach could only detect low quantities of ctDNA [51]. The
25 electrochemical biosensor that was developed using 3D GR/AuPtPd nanoflowers
26 showed remarkable selectivity and performance when tested with human blood (**Fig. 4**) [51].

Fig 4. (I) The CRISPR/Cas9-triggered entropy-driven and displacement reaction (ESDR) is illustrated schematically using a 3D Au/Pd nanoflower biosensor. **(II)** (A) SDS-PAGE analysis of Cas9 proteins. (B) Synthesis of the synthesized sgRNA via gel electrophoresis and (C) DNA samples following the cleavage of Cas9/sgRNA; **(III)** Analytical performance of the DNA biosensor [51]. Copyright © 2021. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

4. CRISPR/Cas9 System for the Fine-Tuning of Cancer Cell Genetic and Epigenetic Regulation

4.1. Advancement in Targeted Delivery of CRISPR/Cas9 for Genome Editing Applications

Cancer treatment is advancing rapidly, with various approaches being explored to develop effective treatment strategies. These include various types of anti-cancer materials, such as chemotherapeutic agents (5-fluorouracil, doxorubicin, vincristine), anti-cancer peptides (ACPs), and radiotherapy, which show optimum outcomes in eliminating cancer cells by either killing or inhibiting their growth [52]. However, administration of these drugs by injection into the bloodstream leads to serious adverse effects. Other than this, there is a problem of rapid metabolism that affects the efficacy of drugs. Thus, there is a need to target cancer loci and drug delivery systems that satisfy the biocompatibility, high-dose loading, and controlled-release approach [53]. As an alternative to conventional drugs, genetic modification tools, like

1 CRISPR/Cas9 technology, which is very useful in treating cancer without causing severe side
 2 effects [54]. The incidence of unwanted off-target effects and the efficacy of genome
 3 modification are both affected by the delivery technique. The delivery of Cas9 and guide RNAs
 4 can be accomplished using ribonucleoprotein, DNA, or RNA/mRNA [55]. To ensure effective
 5 genome editing, CRISPR/Cas9 components are delivered using one of three primary strategies:
 6 physical techniques such as electroporation and microinjection; viral delivery using lentiviral,
 7 adenoviral, or AAV vectors; and non-viral platforms such as plasmid DNA, lipid nanoparticles,
 8 polymeric carriers, and EVs [56]. The optimal delivery method depends on several factors,
 9 including the state of experiments, the kind of cargo used, and the target cell or organ type.
 10 Furthermore, this setting necessitates the consideration of many technical hurdles, such as
 11 specificity, efficiency, the danger of insertional mutagenesis, and the generation of an immune
 12 response. The CRISPR/Cas9 system can be efficiently delivered via microinjection and
 13 electroporation, which also have a high yield of transfected cells. Although these methods are
 14 effective, they are not suitable for use in ex vivo research on zygotes due to their
 15 toxicity [57]. Hamilton et al. introduced Cas9 RNA and a CAK transgene into primary human
 16 T cells via a one-step procedure involving modified lentiviral particles. They can also tailor
 17 particle tropism to target a specific cell type within a mixed cell population. The results show
 18 that particles targeting the HIV-1 envelope can edit CD4+ cells without harming the co-
 19 cultured CD8+ cells, proving the specificity of the method (Fig. 5) [58].

20
 21 **Fig. 5. (I)** Immature immune cells can be engineered using CRISPR-Cas9 and transgenes
 22 delivered to specific locations; **(II) (A)** A schematic of the plasmids used to produce Cas9-
 23 VLP; **(B)** A schematic depicting the process of transient transfection resulting in an immature

1 Cas9-VLP; (C) Western blot analysis of Cas9-VLP concentrations produced using different
2 proportions of Gag-pol and Gag-Cas9 plasmids; (D) Measurement of Cas9-VLP production
3 per transfected p100 dish using CA ELISA; (E) A millilitre titer of transducing units (TUs) was
4 determined after treating jurkats with B2M-targeting Cas9-VLPs; (F) A sigmoidal 4-parameter
5 logistic fit was used to plot the percentage of B2M indels against the multiplicity of infection
6 (MOI). G) The expected MOI for each Cas9-VLP composition is required for 50% DNA
7 damage [58]. Copyright 2021. Adapted from Cell Press.

9 *4.2. Emerging Variants and Functional Expansions of CRISPR/Cas9*

10 CRISPR-Cas9 technology offers a reliable and programmable method for manipulating
11 gene sequences and expression. Recent research has demonstrated site-specific breakage in
12 DNA double strands with the nuclease activity of the Cas9 enzyme [59]. As cancer is often
13 dictated by genetic mutations, the CRISPR/Cas9 system provides a promising approach for
14 correcting the mutated sequences, by editing altered genetic sequences back to normal and non-
15 cancerous.[60]. The targeted DNA endonuclease relies on a sequence-dependent nuclease
16 domain, to induce double-stranded cleavage in DNA at specific locations. This contrasts with
17 earlier known nucleases, which are sequence independent and cleave the DNA non-
18 specifically. As an example of a targeted endonuclease, the RNA-guided endonuclease Cas9
19 has made genome editing accessible to a wider audience by facilitating large-scale, quick
20 genetic editing in any organism of interest [61]. The role of Cas9 in this system is to create
21 small genomic insertions and deletions via NHEJ and facilitate larger sequence manipulation
22 with homologous recombination (HR), making multiplex genome engineering possible [62].
23 The binding and catalytic activity of Cas9 requires a recognition signal, a short DNA sequence
24 (2 – 6 base pair in length), known as the PAM, located adjacent to the target sequence. While
25 Cas9 is primarily a tool for DNA editing, recent evidential research suggests that Cas9 may
26 also target RNA sequences [63]. By using specifically designed PAMmers, Cas 9 can bind and
27 break the RNA targets while avoiding corresponding DNA sequences. This strategy can be
28 used to isolate endogenous mRNA from cells [64]. To trigger an exponential amplification
29 response (EXPAR), Song et al. devised a novel method for DNA mutation detection utilising
30 CRISPR-EXPAR [65]. In this method, the two-complex Cas9/sgRNA CRISPR system was
31 modified to target mutant DNA sequences more precisely, and then to carry out a pattern of
32 repeated extension and nicking to promote EXPAR. As a result, EXPAR products are
33 abundantly produced, and duplex-specific fluorescence labelling may be performed later on.

1 Using this design strategy, they achieved an astounding degree of precision, down to 437 aM,
2 in identifying a HER2 gene mutation as a model target. Another EFGF L858R mutation was
3 found, further confirming its widespread use as shown in **Fig. S3** [65].

4 5 **5. Loading of CRISPR/Cas9 Components in Extravesicular System**

6 Genetic engineering is a complex field that involves modifying genes at the molecular
7 level. Receptor cells can replicate, translate, and express genes from external sources, leading
8 to the production of various functional proteins [66]. The advent of CRISPR-Cas systems
9 heralded a new age in genome editing, which can modify the behavior and function of receptor
10 cells. This technology is derived from the natural defense mechanism used by bacteria to
11 protect themselves against bacteriophage infections. In this system, bacteria recognize and
12 cut the nucleic acids of invading phages. Preventing re-infection and imparting cellular
13 immunity. For the CRISPR-Cas protein to work, it really has to combine with a sgRNA, which
14 is formed by combining trans-activating crRNA (tracrRNA) with CRISPR RNA (crRNA) [67].
15 This complex forms the Cas-sgRNA ribonucleoprotein (RNP), which can be programmed to
16 recognize and cleave specific DNA sequences. Many industries that require gene editing have
17 adopted type II CRISPR-Cas9 because of its high efficiency and ease of use. However, several
18 barriers limit its application in therapy, which include ineffective delivery techniques [68].
19 All cells have endogenous membrane particles called EVs that are discharged into the
20 extracellular environment. They serve as messengers and exchange cargo, facilitating the
21 movement of proteins, nucleic acids, and bioactive lipids between cells [69]. Following inward
22 budding, endosomes grow into intraluminal vesicles before being released as exosomes
23 (30-100 nm) into the extracellular space. For an ectosome to develop, the cell plasma
24 membrane must pinch or bud outward [70]. From a few micrometers to less than 100
25 nanometers, their vesicles range in size. Ectosomes are primarily classified as microvesicles
26 (0.2-1 μm) and large oncosomes ($>1 \mu\text{m}$). The 1-5 μm -long apoptotic bodies include harmful
27 cellular components that persist after apoptosis [71]. According to the increasing amount of
28 data, these many EV types differ greatly in terms of their makeup, modes of operation, and
29 other unique characteristics [72, 73]. However, because of their capacity to pass across
30 biological barriers and transfer bioactive components, they are linked to both physiological and
31 pathological situations as demonstrated in **Fig. 6** [74].

1
 2 **Fig 1** Efficient drug loading into pre-formed extracellular vesicles (EVs) is depicted
 3 schematically. The cargo loading into EVs can be achieved using multiple techniques, such as
 4 passive incubation (a), sonication (b), electroporation (c), extrusion (d), freeze–thaw cycling
 5 (e), saponin-mediated permeabilization (f), and membrane fusion–based methods (g) [74].
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7
 8 Ye et al. developed a functionalized exosome (M-CRISPR-Cas9 exosome) capable of more
 9 efficiently encapsulating CRISPR-Cas9 components [72]. To enhance the loading efficiency
 10 of Cas9 proteins into exosomes, they created artificial exosomes by fusing GFP with the
 11 exosomal membrane protein CD63 and Cas9 with a GFP nanobody. The affinity of the GFP-
 12 GFP nanobody allowed for the effective and selective loading of Cas9 proteins into exosomes,

1 eliminating the need for random loading. A combination consisting of sgRNA and Cas9 protein
2 can be transported into recipient cells through functionalized exosomes. A reporter cell line
3 (A549stop-DsRed) was developed to visually demonstrate the function of modified exosomes-
4 delivered CRISPR-Cas9 components in recipient cells. This line emitted a red fluorescent
5 signal upon deletion of the stop element by the sgRNA-guided endonuclease. They
6 demonstrated, using A549stop-DsRed reporter cells, that recipient cells were more effectively
7 able to abort the target gene when exposed to modified exosomes laden with CRISPR-Cas9
8 components [72]. Moreover, Liu et al. carried out a genome-wide in vivo CRISPR loss-of-
9 function screen in orthotopic tumors in mice undergoing radiation therapy to uncover synthetic
10 lethal genes associated with radiotherapeutic response [73]. A possible regulator of
11 radioresistance through ferroptosis was identified as glutathione synthetase (GSS) by
12 functional screening and transcriptome studies. Patients with glioma had a worse prognosis and
13 were more likely to relapse if their GSS levels were high. The inhibition of radiotherapy-
14 induced ferroptosis in glioma cells was linked to GSS, according to mechanistic studies. The
15 induction of ferroptosis was enhanced by radiation treatment because GSS depletion disrupted
16 glutathione (GSH) synthesis, inactivated GPX4, and caused iron buildup [73]. Additionally, to
17 circumvent the barriers to the widespread therapeutic application of CRISPR editing, we
18 present a novel genome editing delivery system. This system involved loading a Cas9
19 protein/sgRNA complex into a modified extracellular vesicle (EV) that was modified
20 using Angiopep-2 (Ang) and the trans-activator of the transcription (TAT) peptide. The EV
21 was designed to target both the blood-brain barrier (BBB) and GBM, permeating the BBB and
22 penetrating tumors. With minimal off-target gene editing and positive indications of GBM
23 tissue targeting, our encapsulating EVs achieved a high GSS gene editing efficiency in GBM
24 (up to 62%). This study proves that it is possible to find therapeutic targets and possible
25 synthetic killer genes using a mix of neutral genetic screening and CRISPR-Cas9-based gene
26 therapy [73].

27

28 *5.1. EV-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 pDNA delivery*

29 The ability to specifically alter genes that involve in tumour suppression, oncogene
30 regulation, and drug resistance pathways has made the CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing approach
31 revolutionary. Issues with targeted, effective, and safe delivery significantly limit its
32 application in clinical settings [40]. EVs, and exosomes in particular, are gaining popularity as
33 a non-viral delivery method due to their natural origin, minimal immunogenicity, intrinsic
34 biocompatibility, and ability to move proteins, nucleic acids, and small molecules across

1 biological barriers [75]. It is possible to build plasmid DNA (pDNA) containing CRISPR/Cas9
2 components to travel via EVs for genome editing in cancer cells. One can use transfection of
3 EV-producing cells, electroporation, sonication, or extrusion to introduce pDNA into EVs.
4 These altered EVs are taken up by recipient cancer cells through processes called membrane
5 fusion or endocytosis, which deliver the CRISPR machinery intracellularly after administration
6 [18]. The CRISPR/Cas9 system may be used to silence oncogenes (like KRAS or MYC),
7 restore the function of tumour suppressor genes (like TP53), or inactivate genes associated with
8 drug resistance and immune evasion once delivered to target cells. When EVs are made from
9 tumour cells or altered with targeting ligands such as peptides or antibodies, the selectivity and
10 concentration of the CRISPR payload at the tumour location are significantly improved. EVs
11 have several advantages over viral vectors, such as lower immunogenicity, better safety
12 profiles, and less insertional mutagenesis [18]. Nonetheless, a number of challenges remain
13 before one can ensure endosomal escape, maintain the structural integrity of the CRISPR
14 plasmid, maximize EV loading efficiency, and scale up production for clinical translation.
15 CRISPR/Cas9 pDNA transport via EV is a potential new non-viral gene editing technique that
16 might transform the treatment of cancer [76].

17 McAndrews et al., modified exosomes provide an alternate, nonviral delivery mechanism
18 for CRISPR/Cas9 [77]. They show that using commonly available transfection reagents, non-
19 autologous exosomes can carry CRISPR/Cas9 plasmid DNA to cancer cells that are intended
20 to be treated, resulting in the targeted deletion of genes. As a proof-of-principle, they
21 demonstrate in syneic subcutaneous and orthotopic pancreatic cancer models that
22 CRISPR/Cas9-laden exosomes can inhibit tumour growth by destroying pancreatic cancer cells
23 carrying the mutant KrasG12D oncogenic gene. Thus, it provides an appropriate approach for
24 CRISPR/Cas9 gene editing to achieve targeted therapeutic effects [77]. Kannada et al. have
25 created microvesicles with modified minicircle (MC) DNA-encoded prodrug conversion
26 enzymes. Breast carcinoma models were treated with these enzymes [78]. TK-NTR expression
27 was increased in breast cancer cells by microvesicles carrying MCs expressing a TK/NTR
28 fusion protein. TK-NTR-mediated in vivo delivery of prodrugs and TK-NTR destroyed
29 surrounding tumour cells and targeted cells by transforming co-delivered prodrugs into active
30 cytotoxic agents. An in vivo mouse model of bystander impact showed that TK-NTR-encoding
31 MCs must carry at least 1% of tumour cells for therapy to work. MC distribution by
32 microvesicles may enhance gene transfer and efficacious prodrug conversion and tumour cell
33 killing, making it a possible cancer therapeutic method [78]. Additionally, Nebogatova et al.
34 describe a novel technique for transiently transfecting EVs with pDNA utilizing cell-

1 penetrating peptides (CPPs) [79]. Using this technique, they discovered that the receiving cells'
2 levels of luciferase reporter protein expression were 104 times higher than those of the
3 untreated cells. These findings demonstrate the supplied encapsulated nucleic acid's excellent
4 transfection effectiveness and bioavailability. Additionally, the in vivo experimental results
5 show that the harmful effects of conventional nucleic acid (NA) delivery and therapy are
6 reduced when pDNA-loaded EVs are used as native delivery vehicles [79]. **Table 1** presents
7 EVs and CRISPR/Cas9 plasmid facilitated gene editing.

Preprint

Table 1: Extracellular vesicle-facilitated gene editing using CRISPR/Cas9 plasmids.

EVs source	Cargo	Loading method	Target gene	Animal model	Outcomes	Ref.
HEK293FT	CRISPR/Cas9 plasmid DNA	Simple incubation	<i>hCTNNB1</i>	C57BL	Efficiently encapsulate a large plasmid	[80]
CD19 CAR-modified epithelial cell-derived EVs	CRISPR/Cas9-sgRNA	Electroporation	MYC	NOD/SCID	Reverse detrimental effects on cancerous B-cells through mutations	[81]
Cancer-derived exosomes	CRISPR/Cas9-sgRNA	Electroporation	PARP-1	BALB/c	Through cell tropism and SKOV3 apoptotic cell death, cisplatin and SKOV3 have a synergistic anti-tumor impact.	[82]
Microvesicles	Plasmid DNA	Lipofection	Cre recombinase	Transgenic Cre-lox reporter mice, Cre-lox Luc reporter mice, BALB/c mice	Introduce Cre recombinase-encoding DNA into living organisms using microvesicles.	[83]
Pancreatic cancer cells derived non-autologous exosomes	CRISPR/Cas9 plasmid DNA	Transfection	<i>KrasG12D</i>	B6-albino mice	Reduced tumour development and proliferation in vivo by eliminating mutant <i>KrasG12D</i> oncogenic alleles.	[77]
Epithelial cell-derived MVs	CRISPR/Cas9	Electroporation	QGAP1	HepG2 positive tumor bearing mice	Better and safer than cancer-derived MVs for CRISPR/Cas9 delivery; inhibits cell growth more effectively.	[84]
HEK293T cells	mRNA, Protein	Transfection	Nef	-	EVs loaded with mRNA and proteins are delivered and targeted to cells successfully.	[85]
Calu-3 and A549 cells	mRNA	Transduction	CFTR	-	CFTR chloride channel function by introducing CFTR glycoprotein and the mRNA that codes for it into cells that lack CFTR.	[86]

HEK293T cells	Cre Recombinase	-		Ndfip 1	knockout mice	Unique mechanism to load protein into EVs by linking Cre recombinase with WW domains, allowing their secretion into the extracellular area.	[87]
Liver AML12 cells	pDNA		Transfection	HNF4 α	C57BL/6	Efficient and fast, but may cause cancer and have unintended side effects.	[88]
Human iPSCs, HEK293T cells	Cas9 sgRNA	protein,	Chemical induced dimerization	Dystrophin	C57BL/6 J mice	Quantitative evaluations of transfer activity; high-efficiency loading; adaptability; and high-activity gene editing	[89]
Dendritic cells	pDNA		Incubation	MMP-11	-	Uncertain long-term safety, minimal gene editing efficiency, intact structure, and simplicity	[90]
Hepatic stellate cells	RNPs		Electrophoresis	<i>Ccn1</i> , <i>E1</i> , and <i>KAT5</i>	C57BL/6, BALB/c	Reproducible operations, high loading efficiency, and no risk of gene transfer	[91]

Preprint

1 5.2. *EV-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 mRNA delivery*

2 Emerging programmable therapy modalities that target the damaged human genome with
3 high specificity and substantial flexibility include RNA treatments, such as CRISPR–Cas9
4 gRNAs, antisense oligonucleotides (ASOs), and siRNAs [92]. However, due to the intrinsic
5 targeting biases of existing delivery systems, chemically modified ASOs and siRNAs are still
6 primarily restricted to the liver and central nervous system, despite some progressing into
7 clinical trials [93]. Viruses (such as adenoviruses, lentiviruses, and retroviruses), lipid
8 transfection agents, and lipid nanoparticles are common vehicles for RNA drug delivery, and
9 they are often cytotoxic and/or immunogenic. As a result, the safe and efficient method for
10 delivering RNA medications to the majority of basic tissues and cancer cells, including solid
11 tumor cells and leukemia cells, continues to be a significant challenge. One important benefit
12 of exosomes for mRNA transport is their capacity to encapsulate RNAs, especially mRNA [94].
13 Exosomes have an intriguing and potential role in delivering mRNA as a medication delivery
14 mechanism. Exosomes give the laden payloads a protected habitat. Exosomes lipid bilayers
15 shield mRNA from extracellular enzyme breakdown, maintaining its stability and integrity as
16 it travels to the target cells. Additionally, the exosome biofilm covering prevents macrophages
17 from breaking them down, thereby extending the duration of circulation [95].

18 Ye et al. developed sgRNA: Cas9 complex for the treatment of tumor. A pair of sgRNAs
19 instructed EV-delivered Cas9 proteins from donor cells to eliminate a blocking sequence,
20 which restored FP expression in recipient reporter cells [96]. Therefore, cells that are
21 fluorescently lit show that EVs are being absorbed. They enhanced the sgRNA design to more
22 effectively stimulate the production of reporter proteins more effectively, increasing the
23 tracking system's sensitivity and efficiency. Moreover, they showed that EVs can cause
24 crosstalk between tumor cells as well as between tumor cells and healthy cells.
25 They demonstrated that EVs given intravenously may be absorbed by the liver. Furthermore,
26 they demonstrated that EVs produced from melanoma xenografts preferentially target the liver
27 and brain. This pattern is similar to how melanoma organotrophic metastases appear. This work
28 offers a different method for examining tumor EV absorption and distribution [96]. Usman et
29 al. described and validated a novel method for producing vast quantities of RBC-derived EVs.
30 The safe and effective delivery of RNA therapeutics using RBCEVs has been demonstrated in
31 both human cells and xenograft animal models to exhibit substantial microRNA interference
32 and CRISPR-Cas9 genome editing [97].

33
34

1 5.3. EV-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 RNPs delivery

2 A potent tool for accurate gene modification in cancer treatment is the CRISPR/Cas9
3 genome editing system. In contrast to plasmid or mRNA delivery, RNPs (ribonucleoproteins),
4 which are preassembled complexes of Cas9 protein and guide RNA (gRNA), provide
5 transitory, non-integrative, and less off-target editing [98]. However, achieving effective,
6 tumor-targeted, and secure intracellular administration of these large biomacromolecular
7 complexes is still a problem. Owing to their natural capacity to transport useful biomolecules
8 between cells, EVs, such as exosomes and microvesicles, have drawn a lot of interest as
9 biocompatible and less immunogenic carriers [99]. In preclinical cancer models, engineering
10 EVs to carry Cas9 RNPs has shown potential. These EVs can be loaded post-isolation using
11 membrane fusion, lipofection, or electroporation methods, or they can be generated from donor
12 cells modified to produce Cas9 and gRNA [100]. To improve tumor-specific delivery, targeting
13 moieties like aptamers, peptides, or antibodies can be loaded to the EV surface. When cancer
14 cells internalize the EVs, they release Cas9 RNPs into the cytoplasm, which allows oncogenes
15 or drug resistance genes to be edited [101]. This can restore chemotherapy sensitivity, stop the
16 growth of the cancer cells, or trigger death. For example, in a variety of cancer models, EV-
17 RNP systems have been effectively employed to delete genes such as PLK1, KRAS, and PD-
18 L1. Additionally, EV-based CRISPR/Cas9 gene editing may have synergistic anticancer
19 benefits when combined with immune checkpoint inhibition or nanotherapeutics [102].
20 Notwithstanding its promise, issues such as in vivo stability, cargo-loading effectiveness, and
21 large-scale EV production still exist. However, the delivery of Cas9 RNP via EVs is a
22 revolutionary approach to precision oncology, providing safe, effective, and targeted gene
23 editing treatment for a variety of cancers [103].

24 Zhuo et al. created valency-controlled tetrahedral DNA nanostructures (TDNs) coupled
25 with DNA aptamer [104]. They then loaded the valency-aptamers-controlled TDNs onto the
26 EV surface using cholesterol anchoring. Investigations were conducted on the targeting
27 effectiveness of various aptamer/cholesterol ratios in TDNs on decorating EVs, ranging from
28 1:3 to 3:1. In xenograft tumor models, human primary liver cancer-derived organoids, and
29 cultured HepG2 cells, TDNs containing one aptamer and three cholesterol anchors (TDN1)
30 effectively promoted the tumor-specific accumulation of the EVs. GFP or WNT10B was
31 downregulated in particular cells as a result of the effective genome editing that followed RNP's
32 intracellular delivery by TDN1-EVs. The findings offer a framework for EV-based Cas9
33 delivery and aptamer-directed display on surface labeling, which provides a useful concept for
34 upcoming cell-selective gene editing [104].

1 Yao et al. enhanced RNPs into EVs by means of the aptamer-binding protein (ABP)-RNA
2 aptamer interaction [105]. By creating a complex with a CD63-Com fusion protein, com-
3 modified sgRNA, and either Cas9 or ABE, they found that the Com/com interaction enhanced
4 the incorporation of Cas9 and adenine base editor (ABE) RNPs into EVs. Genome editing is
5 made possible by the RNP-enriched EVs, which are expressed transiently. Delivering RNPs
6 that target several loci allows the system to do multiplex genome editing. In addition, Cas9
7 from different species might be mixed. The results suggest that RNPs can be efficiently and
8 safely enriched into EVs through interactions between aptamers and ABPs, leading to
9 improved genome editing efficiency [105].

11 *5.4. EV-mediated CRISPR/Cas9 sgRNA delivery*

12 The use of CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing to selectively delete or fix genes associated with
13 cancer has greatly improved cancer research and treatment [106]. Two essential parts of this
14 system are transported: the Cas9 endonuclease and sgRNA, which points Cas9 toward the
15 target genomic location [107]. The specificity and effectiveness of this system are dependent
16 on this delivery. Even though getting both parts to the right place is still tough, researchers have
17 recently looked at using EVs as sgRNA carriers since they are biocompatible and naturally
18 occurring. The sgRNA delivery is a promising use for EVs, particularly exosomes, due to their
19 inherent capacity to transport functional RNA and protein cargo across cells [108]. During
20 biogenesis, by transfecting donor cells with sgRNA-expressing constructs, or post-isolation,
21 by methods including electroporation, transfection, or hybridization, EVs can be designed to
22 incorporate sgRNA [109]. Cells expressing Cas9 endogenously or those that have received
23 Cas9 protein or sgRNA separately can be mixed with these sgRNA-loaded EVs. This method
24 of divided distribution permits temporal regulation of genome editing while also decreasing
25 off-target effects [110]. Using EV-mediated sgRNA delivery in conjunction with Cas9 has
26 demonstrated promise in cancer models for regressing tumors, reducing proliferation, or
27 making cancer more sensitive to chemotherapeutics by knocking down important
28 oncogenes, including KRAS, MYC, or BCL-2. Additionally, aptamers, tumor-homing
29 peptides, or antibodies added to the surface of EVs can improve absorption to cancer cells. This
30 method has a lot of promise for systemic administration with low immunogenicity or for
31 targeting tumors that are difficult to reach. Nevertheless, there are still obstacles to overcome,
32 such as improving the efficiency of sgRNA loading, evading endosomes, and producing
33 functioning EVs on a large scale [111]. The use of EVs to deliver sgRNA, particularly in

1 conjunction with Cas9-based tools, is a promising new approach to cancer gene therapy that is
2 targeted, non-viral, and tailored to each patient.

3 Liu et al utilised CRISPR/Cas9 system for the treatment of glioblastoma [112]. To uncover
4 synthetic lethal genes related to irradiation, an in vivo loss-of-function genome-wide CRISPR
5 screen was performed in orthotopic tumors in radiation-treated mice. Glutathione synthetase
6 (GSS) was identified as a possible ferroptosis-mediated regulator of radioresistance by
7 functional screening and transcriptome studies. Recurrence and a poor prognosis were strongly
8 associated with high GSS levels in glioma patients. In glioma cells, mechanistic investigations
9 showed that GSS inhibited radiation-induced ferroptosis. The development of ferroptosis was
10 enhanced by radiation treatment because GSS depletion disrupted glutathione (GSH)
11 production, inactivated GPX4, and caused iron buildup [112]. In addition, they presented a
12 novel genome editing delivery system that traverses the blood-brain barrier (BBB) and GBM,
13 penetrating both, to circumvent the challenges to widespread therapeutic translation of
14 CRISPR editing. This system consists of an Angiopoietin-1 (Ang) and a trans-activator of
15 transcription (TAT) peptide dual-modified EVs, which they loaded with a Cas9 protein/sgRNA
16 complex. They found promising evidence of GBM tissue targeting with our encapsulating EVs,
17 leading to a high GSS gene editing efficiency in GBM (up to 67.2%), with almost little off-
18 target gene editing. These findings show that it is possible to find possible synthetic killer genes
19 and, consequently, treatment targets by combining CRISPR-Cas9-based gene therapy with
20 impartial genetic screening [112].

21 Dubey et al. created the modular safeEXO platform, a model sEV delivery vehicle that is
22 mostly free of endogenous RNA [100]. In addition, they were able to successfully design
23 producer cells to generate safeEXO vehicles with endogenous Cas9 (safeEXO-CAS). These
24 vehicles efficiently transport the RNP mediated CRISPR genome editing machinery to
25 unhealthy cells or organs both in the lab and in the blood. This study validates the ability of
26 safeEXO-CAS EVs to facilitate gene insertion in a dose-dependent manner while
27 simultaneously delivering ssDNA, sgRNA, and siRNA. By designing sEVs to express integrin
28 alpha-6, a tissue-specific moiety, they were able to boost their uptake by lung epithelial cells,
29 demonstrating the ability to target safeEXO-CAS sEVs (safeEXO-CAS-ITGA6) [100]. The
30 results showed that there was considerable gene editing in the lungs without any noticeable
31 alterations in immune cell populations or symptoms of illness. Using our modular safeEXO
32 technology, they were able to successfully transport nucleic acid-based therapies to their
33 intracellular targets safely and effectively. To make RNP-mediated genome editing even more
34 effective, it is possible to genetically modify safeEXO producer cells such that they create

1 safeEXO vehicles equipped with CRISPR machinery. With its RNA interference (RNAi) and
2 CRISPR capabilities, this platform may enhance existing treatments and open up new insights
3 for various human disorders [100].

4 5 **6. Drug delivery strategies for CRISPR/Cas9 technology in cancer therapy**

6 *6.1. Chemical/Peptide-Enhanced Delivery of CRISPR/Cas9 System for Cancer Therapy*

7 A revolutionary tool for targeted gene editing in cancer treatment, the CRISPR/Cas9 system
8 can eliminate tumor-promoting genes, repair oncogenic mutations, and boost anti-tumor
9 immunity. Problems with delivery, such as inadequate cellular absorption, off-target effects,
10 and degradation in the biological environment, severely restrict its clinical translation [113].
11 Delivery methods based on chemicals and peptides have attracted a lot of interest as potential
12 solutions to these problems. Systems such as lipid-based complexes, pH-responsive polymers,
13 and cell-penetrating peptides (CPPs) allow CRISPR components to be localized in the nucleus,
14 escape from endosomes, and transit efficiently throughout cells [114]. These approaches reduce
15 toxicity and immunological responses while increasing bioavailability, targeting, and stability
16 of the CRISPR/Cas9 machinery. Treatment results can be improved by engineering peptide-
17 functionalized nanocarriers to enable tumor-specific targeting [115]. Liu et al. developed
18 natural polymer-based multi-functional self-assembled nanoparticles [116]. A multi-functional
19 outer layer was added to the virus-like particle (VLP)-based gene editing plasmid to delete the CDK11 gene.
20 This layer consisted of an endocytolytic peptide (KALA) and aptamer AS1411 integrated
21 carboxymethyl chitosan. The complex was then decorated with protamine sulfate. Due to the
22 combination of AS1411 ligand affinity to target cancer cells and cell nuclei and KALA's
23 beneficial effect on cellular uptake and endosomal escape, the resulting multi-functional
24 nanoparticles show dramatically improved delivery efficiency and can deliver the plasmid into
25 tumor cell nuclei [116]. The nanoparticle-mediated genome editing causes a significant
26 reduction (>75%) in CDK11 expression, which in turn modulates cancer cells by up-regulating
27 the tumor suppressor protein p53 and down-regulating the proteins (MMP-9 and VEGF)
28 involved in tumor development and metastasis [116].

29 Cancer cells secrete exosomes, which can transport CRISPR/Cas9 plasmids to cancer
30 cells, was investigated by Kim et al [82]. They concentrate specifically in the ovarian cancer
31 tumors of SKOV3 xenograft mice, cancer-derived exosomes are thought to be a potential
32 carrier for efficient in vivo administration due to their cell tropism. By inhibiting the expression
33 of PARP-1, exosomes loaded with CRISPR/Cas9 can induce cell death in ovarian cancer. Parp-
34 1 reduction using CRISPR/Cas9-mediated genome editing enhances chemosensitivity to

1 cisplatin, demonstrating synergistic cytotoxicity. According to the results, tumor-derived
2 exosomes show a lot of promise as a potential new cancer treatment [82]. To find synthetic
3 lethal genes related to irradiation, Liu et al. conducted an in vivo loss-of-function genome-wide
4 CRISPR screen in orthotopic tumours in radiation-treated mice [112]. Glutathione synthetase
5 (GSS) was identified as a possible ferroptosis-mediated regulator of radioresistance by
6 functional screening and transcriptome studies. Recurrence and a poor prognosis were strongly
7 associated with high GSS levels in glioma patients. In glioma cells, mechanistic investigations
8 showed that GSS inhibited radiation-induced ferroptosis. The induction of ferroptosis was
9 enhanced by radiation treatment because GSS depletion disrupted glutathione (GSH) synthesis,
10 inactivated GPX4, and caused iron buildup. In addition, a novel genome editing delivery
11 system was developed to circumvent the barriers to CRISPR editing, widespread therapeutic
12 translation [112]. This system involved loading a Cas9 protein-sgRNA complex into a dual-
13 modified extracellular vesicle (EV) that was modified using Angiogenin-2 (Ang2) and the trans-
14 activator of the transcription (TAT) peptide. The EV was designed to target both the BBB and
15 GBM, and it was able to penetrate both the BBB and the tumour. High GSS gene editing
16 efficiency in GBM (up to 67.2% with minimal off-target gene editing) was achieved by
17 the encapsulating EVs, which demonstrated promising GBM tissue targeting. These findings
18 show that it is possible to find possible synthetic killer genes and, consequently, treatment
19 targets by combining CRISPR Cas9 based gene therapy with impartial genetic screening (**Fig.**
20 **7(I)** [112]. In another work, Liu et al. developed targeted therapy of Cas9/sgrNA for antitumor
21 effect [117]. In the presence of calcium ions, protamine was used to compact the Cas9/sgrNA
22 plasmid into nanosized cores. These cores were then decorated with alginate derivatives
23 coupled with peptides and aptamers. Mutations in the genome trigger cell death in tumours,
24 however, this cell death must occur in the mitochondria [117]. Also, the PI3K/AKT signalling
25 pathway is negatively regulated by FAK deletion. Meanwhile, genome editing allows for the
26 realization of beneficial modulation on many proteins involved in tumour advancement.
27 Genome editing appears to have the desired impact of reducing tumour formation, as indicated
28 by the increased E-cadherin and decreased MMPs, vimentin, and VEGF. Verified by wound
29 healing and transwell experiments, the genome editing technique effectively inhibits tumour
30 invasion and metastasis in modified cells (**Fig. 7(II)** [117].

1
 2 **Fig. 7.** (I) Radiation sensitization of glioblastoma via engineered extracellular vesicles (EV)
 3 delivered CRISPR/Cas9 [112]. Copyright 2023. Adapted from the American Chemical Society.
 4 (II) Genome editing plasmid delivery to tumours and development of a peptide and aptamer
 5 functionalized gene delivery system [117]. Copyright 2023. Reproduced with permission from
 6 the American Chemical Society.

7
 8

6.2. Light-Enhanced Delivery of CRISPR/Cas9 System

A significant benefit of this approach over conventional stimuli, such as radio radiation, is the absence of adverse side effects on exposed tissues. The use of light to release gene-editing payloads offers more benefits than other methods. This is because it allows the carrier to escape from the endosome and remotely manage the editing of the target tissue. Gene editing tools can be transported and activated by light, providing a non-invasive, geographical, and temporal solution [118]. Light can physically and chemically change a variety of materials. Luminescent materials produce photon-up conversion, photosensitizing compounds cause reactive oxygen species generation, and light-induced photothermal effects are caused by photothermal agents [119]. One such example is the nano-platform presented by Chen et al., which combines gene therapy, photothermal therapy, and chemotherapy and is triggered by near-infrared light (NIR) [120]. The thiol group was functionalized onto the surface of the CuS NPs. Then, DNA segments carrying attached Cas9/sgRNA were conjugated to them utilizing base complementary pairing to load doxorubicin. Photothermal CuS NPs released doxorubicin and Cas9/sgRNA RNP as they sped up the disintegration of DNA fragment-sgRNA hybridization [120]. This was achieved by converting near-infrared light (808 nm) into heat. The ability of tumor cells for thermal tolerance and metastasis was diminished as a result of the downregulation of Hsp90 α expression, a subunit of Hsp90, by RNPs that targeted the Hsp90 gene. Additionally, the heat action induced by CuS NPs had the potential to be destroyed by tumor cells [120].

Zhao et al. designed a light-activated degradable CRISPR/Cas9 nanosystem that targets PD-L1 gene editing under NIR-II irradiation, offering enhanced tumor immunogenicity through immune checkpoint blockade and metabolic reprogramming [121]. In this study, they created biodegradable photothermal nanocarriers (RPP) using cationic polymers and rough polydopamine nanoparticles to achieve PD-L1 targeting with second near-infrared (NIR-II) light-activated CRISPR/Cas9 and tumor glycolysis inhibition by resveratrol (Res). Transforming the immunosuppressive TME is possible with the simultaneous delivery of CRISPR/Cas9 plasmids controlled by a heat-inducible promoter (pHCP) and natural Res. This allows for the permanent editing of the PD-L1 gene and the management of glucose metabolism [121]. In the presence of NIR light, the photothermal effect of RPP causes tumor cells to undergo immunogenic cell death (ICD), which in turn triggers the release of Res and drives the transcription of single-guide RNA targeting PD-L1 and Cas9. These events help activate immune responses that fight against tumors. Furthermore, the immune response is boosted by utilizing the intrinsic immunomodulatory activities of the RPP nanocarriers [121].

1 For example; a permanent blockage of PD-L1 and reconfiguration of the immunosuppressive
2 TME are achieved by the suggested RPP-mediated treatment method as shown in **Fig. S4** [121].

4 *6.3. Glutathione-Triggered Delivery of CRISPR/Cas9 System*

5 There has been research toward a method that could improve the efficiency of both delivery
6 and editing, execution that is responsive to glutathione (GSH) [122]. This strategy aims to
7 enhance the release of genetic cargo. In the cytosol, the concentration of GSH is 2-10 mM,
8 which is about 1000 times higher than in the extracellular compartment, where it ranges from
9 2-20 μ M [123]. The disulfide bridge has been examined extensively as a pH-responsive linker
10 and as a potential target for intracellular GSH-induced thiol-disulfide exchange. In vivo
11 genome editing has great therapeutic promise, but efficient intracellular transport of
12 CRISPR/Cas9 components is a big hurdle. Glutathione (GSH)-responsive systems are a new
13 and selective method for delivering gene-editing machinery to the cytosol out of several
14 possible delivery options [124]. As a tripeptide antioxidant, glutathione is suitable for
15 triggering the release of cargo within cells, as it is available at high concentrations within cells
16 (~2-10 mM) and at extremely low levels outside cells (2-20 μ M) [125]. A lot of nanocarriers
17 have disulfide or diselenide linkers that are cleaved in the reducing cytosolic environment, and
18 this redox gradient works well for that. Encapsulating CRISPR/Cas9 components, whether as
19 plasmid DNA, mRNA, or even complete CRISPR/Cas9 disulfide-crosslinked nanocarriers like
20 polymeric nanoparticles, liposomes, micelles, or mesoporous silica nanoparticles, is the
21 process that GSH-triggered systems employ. As the CRISPR/Cas9 payload is quickly released
22 into the cytosol during cellular uptake by endocytosis, the carrier becomes unstable due to the
23 disulfide bonds being broken by the elevated intracellular GSH content [114]. The efficiency
24 of gene editing is improved, while off-target effects and premature leaks are minimized, leading
25 to this controlled release.

26 In a study, Wang et al. developed a method for delivering the CRISPR-Cas9 RNA plasmid
27 to target nasopharyngeal cancer gene therapy using a glutathione-sensitive cationic polymer
28 [126]. Conjugated with the cyclic RGD (Arg-Gly-Asp) for the targeted treatment of
29 nasopharyngeal cancer (NPC), glutathione-sensitive cationic vectors, hyperbranched
30 polyamide amine (HPAA) were developed for the delivery of the CRISPR-Cas9 RNA plasmid.
31 High glutathione concentrations in tumor microenvironments can trigger disulfide bond
32 responses in HPAA segments [126]. On the other hand, RGD has the potential to specifically
33 engage with the integrin α v β 3 receptors found on the surface of NPC tumor cells. After RGD
34 was attached, the results demonstrated that NPC HNE-1 cells could ingest more HPAA-

1 RGD/SGK3-gRNA complexes. The plasmid could then accumulate in the NPC tumor as well,
2 suggesting that the NPC therapeutic effect *in vivo* may be achieved. This compound
3 demonstrated a promising applicability in gene therapy for NPC in transfection experiments,
4 with acceptable gene transfection efficiency *in vitro* and an evident tumor reduction impact *in*
5 *vivo* **Fig. 8(I)** [126]. In another study, Zou et al. designed nanocapsules of Cas9/sgPLK-1 for
6 effective and safe glioblastoma gene therapy [127]. Due to GSH responsiveness, the ANCs
7 can release the labeled Cas9 protein from the carrier, which prevents the fluorescence
8 quenching that occurs due to delayed drug release. Also, out of all the genes tested, 36.6%
9 mutated due to disulfide bonds and 9.8% mutated due to anything else. Successfully releasing
10 CRISPR/Cas9 allows them to conclude that gene editing effects can be improved [127]. In
11 another work, a stimulus-responsive silica nanoparticle (SNP) that can regulate nanoparticle
12 size (~50 nm) was developed by Wang et al., and it was found to be capable of encapsulating
13 active biomacromolecules [128]. When target cells absorb SNP, they gain the ability to release
14 cargo that is sensitive to glutathione (GSH) due to a disulfide crosslinker that was incorporated
15 into the silica network. To improve the endosomal escape capabilities, the SNP was engineered
16 to include an imidazole-containing component. Various targeting ligands can be functionalized
17 onto the SNP surface through PEGylation. Results from *in vivo* experiments demonstrated that
18 mRNA and RNP can be efficiently delivered to cells and liver respectively as depicted in **Fig.**
19 **8(II)** [128].

1
 2 **Fig 8.** (I) A schematic depicting the steps involved in preparing and internalizing the
 3 hyperbranched polyamide amine (HPAA)-RGD [126]. Copyright 2023. Reproduced with
 4 permission from Elsevier. (II) Diagrammatic representation of the SNP intracellular transport
 5 routes. (III) Conceptualization and production of silica nanoparticle (SNPs) coupled with
 6 ATRA or GalNAc [128]. Copyright 2021. Reproduced with permission from Elsevier.

1 6.4. pH-Responsive Delivery of CRISPR/Cas9 System

2 The gene-editing tool known as CRISPR/Cas9 has revolutionized gene therapy and
3 molecular biology. However, difficulties in delivering CRISPR/Cas9 in a safe, focused, and
4 effective manner have severely impeded its clinical translation [129]. As a result of the acidic
5 extracellular pH common in disease-specific microenvironments like tumours or inflamed
6 tissues, pH-responsive nanocarriers have attracted a lot of interest as a stimuli-responsive
7 delivery strategy for CRISPR/Cas9 administration [130]. To allow for regulated release of the
8 CRISPR components, these smart delivery systems undergo structural or functional
9 modifications in acidic conditions, while remaining stable at physiological pH. In addition to
10 reducing off-target effects and systemic toxicity, pH-responsive methods improve intracellular
11 delivery and endosomal escape of CRISPR/Cas9. Therefore, a practical strategy for achieving
12 spatiotemporal control over CRISPR/Cas9 delivery for precision genome editing in clinical
13 applications is to build pH-sensitive platforms [131].

14 Liu et al. developed core-shell tecto dendrimers loaded with gold nanoparticles and
15 reactive oxygen species (ROS) that can respond to changes in pH [132]. These dendrimers,
16 called Au CSTDs, can transport a CRISPR/Cas9 system that permanently disrupts the PD-L1
17 gene in cancer cells. This research involved building Au CSTDs with phenylboronic acid
18 (PBA)-conjugated generation 3 dendrimers serving as shells and gold nanoparticles embedded
19 in dendrimers of generation 5 that were modified with lactobionic acid (LA) serving as cores.
20 This was achieved by forming responsive phenylborate ester bonds between the two groups.
21 Successful compacting and uptake of the plasmid-CRISPR/Cas9 system by cancer cells
22 overexpressing sialic acids is achieved through PBA-mediated targeting [132]. Then, the Au
23 CSTDs can be responsively released into the cancer cells, allowing them to successfully escape
24 endosomal confinement and effectively knock out the PD-L1 gene. Using a mouse melanoma
25 model for further in vivo delivery, they found that the Au CSTDs/plasmid-CRISPR/Cas9
26 complexes can be targeted to tumour sites for improved CT imaging of tumours (due to Au's
27 X-ray attenuation effect) and can disrupt PD-L1 expression in tumour cells, promoting ICB-
28 based antitumor immunity (**Fig. S5(I)**) [132]. In another work, Li et al. developed a hybrid
29 delivery method that combines PLPNs with UMMD. PLPNs may be efficiently engineered to
30 carry the CRISPRi plasmid, which extends their duration in the bloodstream and allows them
31 to "actively target" cancer cells [133]. Additionally, the CRISPRi plasmid is better taken up by
32 cells in vitro and retained in vivo when PLPNs and UMMD are combined. A combination of
33 UMMD and PLPNs loaded with a CRISPRi plasmid targeting microRNA-10b (miR-10b)
34 effectively represses miR-10b in breast cancer, disrupts signaling pathways related to invasion

- 1 and multiple cell migration at the same time, and significantly inhibits lung metastasis.
- 2 Delivering the CRISPRi system in vitro and in vivo has never been easier than with the existing
- 3 technology, which is adaptable, efficient, and safe (**Fig. S5II**) [133].

Preprint

7. Imaging techniques of nanomaterials loaded with CRISPR/Cas9 components for cancer therapy

7.1. Fluorescence-based imaging of nanomaterials loaded with CRISPR/Cas9 components for cancer therapy

One revolutionary method in cancer theranostics is the use of fluorescent imaging to detect nanomaterials encased in CRISPR/Cas9 components. This method allows for the precise administration of therapeutics and the real-time viewing of gene-editing activities. Researchers can observe the biodistribution, cellular uptake, and genome-editing efficacy in tumor microenvironments by incorporating CRISPR/Cas9 into fluorescently labelable nanocarriers like liposomes, polymeric nanoparticles, gold nanoclusters, or upconversion nanoparticles [11]. In addition to enhancing the temporal and geographical resolution of treatments, this technique allows for site-specific administration and real-time tracking, which in turn lowers off-target effects. It is possible to conduct non-invasive in vivo imaging utilizing confocal, NIR, or multiphoton fluorescence microscopy due to fluorescent tags or probes that are either intrinsic to the nanocarrier or coupled to the Cas9/sgRNA complex [12]. For individualized cancer treatment, these integrated systems have tremendous promise, especially for tracking tumor response, verifying delivery effectiveness, and fine-tuning dosage plans. This method opens the door to cancer therapies based on gene editing that are less invasive and more effective.

Zhang et al. developed a fluorogenic CRISPR-Cas9 system, fCRISPR [135]. A fluorogenic protein, an engineered sgRNA, and Cas9 are the building blocks of fCRISPR. If fluorogenic proteins are not coupled to certain RNA hairpins, they will be broken down. Fluorogenic DNA imaging is made possible by creating dCas9-sgRNA: fluorogenic protein ternary complexes by inserting these hairpins into sgRNA. The dynamics and length of chromosomes may also be tracked using fCRISPR. DNA double-strand breaks (DSBs) and repair may also be monitored in real-time using fCRISPR. All things considered, fCRISPR provides a sensitive and high-contrast platform for imaging genomic loci (**Fig. 9**) [135]. In another study, Heath et al. develop a DNA biosensor that delivers a sensitive readout for such low-copy DNA sequences [136]. By utilizing our "turn-on" probe in living cells, we show that it can identify specific endogenous genomic loci using conventional epifluorescence microscopy, an application that is not easily accomplished with fluorescent reporter-based probes [136]. In addition to providing a solid foundation for a wide variety of other live cell DNA biosensing applications, this method has the potential to allow for the detection of gene modifications during ex vivo editing operations [136].

1
 2 **Fig 9. (I) (a)** Fluorogenic protein structure diagram using pepper-stabilized fCRISPR; (b)
 3 Genomic locus labeling comparison between fCRISPR and traditional CRISPR using dCas9-
 4 GFP and tdTomato-tDeg reporters (white arrows); c) Chromosome 3 was the only target of
 5 fCRISPR, which did not show any nonspecific accumulation of fluorescence in the nucleolus
 6 (yellow arrow). **(II)** Analysis of relative telomere length in a single cell using fCRISPR with
 7 tdTomato-tDeg vs CRISPR with dCas9-GFP [135]. Copyright 2024. Adapted from Springer
 8 Nature.

7.2. Confocal microscopy imaging of nanomaterials loaded with CRISPR/Cas9 components for cancer therapy

Confocal microscopy employs a spatial pinhole to eliminate out-of-focus light, leading to micrographs with improved contrast and resolution. In biological research in particular, it allows for the capture of high-resolution, three-dimensional pictures of specimens [137]. Using this technology, one can see nanoparticles, cellular architecture, and drug delivery systems within living cells or tissue slices, with tremendous value. It is possible to visualize complex biological matrices to identify specific targets using confocal microscopy and fluorescent dyes or labels. It also facilitates the use of time-lapse imaging for monitoring dynamic processes, such as intracellular trafficking or nanoparticle absorption. Utilizing Z-stack creation to reconstruct 3D images results in the extraction of fine-grained image data [138]. Researchers investigating biological systems and medications greatly benefit from confocal microscopy.

Yu et al. developed a self-driven multifunctional delivery vector to disseminate the CRISPR-Cas9 nanosystem [139]. One such self-driven safety probiotic is *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG (LGG), which may efficiently transport the CRISPR/Cas9 system to the tumour location by penetrating the hypoxic tumour centre. The efficient colonisation of the tumour area by LGG is accompanied by its ability to stimulate the organism's immune system. Under ultrasonic irradiation, the CRISPR/Cas9 nanosystem can produce a great deal of ROS, leading to induced cell death (ICD) [140]. When ROS triggers endosomal/lysosomal rupture, Cas9/sgRNA is released, which knocks down the PD01 gene and lifts immunosuppression. In a mouse model, the system inhibits tumour re-challenge by producing immune responses that kill tumour cells. Furthermore, this approach safeguards against lung metastases through an immunological memory effect (**Fig 10 (I&II)**) [139]. In another work, Ruan et al. created a CRISPR-Cas9-based nanomedicine through developing a polymeric nanoparticle that was coated with angiopoep-2 and functionalized with guanidinium and fluorine [140]. The nanoparticle was loaded with Cas9 and gRNA RNP. To stabilize Cas9/gRNA RNP in blood circulation without compromising its action, their polymeric nanoparticles guanidinium and fluorine domains interacted (**Fig 10 (III)**) [140]. Additionally, a calcium phosphate-based nanomedicine delivery method for RNP was described by Wei et al., which effectively targets the EphA2 mutation for CRPC gene therapy [141]. An sgRNA intended to target the EphA2 genomic region is combined with Cas9 endonuclease to produce RNP. Moreover, "RNP@CaP-TAT" describes the delivery nanoparticles that are formed when Cas9 RNP is further complexed with a compound (Ca-TAT) after CaCl₂ and TAT have been mixed. With a calcium phosphate core, this nanoparticle has excellent delivery and biosafety properties, and it has

1 successfully inhibited cell migration in vitro. This opens the door to a safe next step in CRPC
 2 gene therapy, specifically in the inhibition of tumor metastasis [141].

3
 4 **Fig 10.** (I) Diagram depicting the Lactobacillus rhamnosus GG (LGG)-MHS nanosystem's
 5 delivery of the CRISPR/Cas9 system for reprogramming the TIME through immune response
 6 activation. (II) a) Process for synthesising LGG-MHS; b) material structure diagrams of ZIF-
 7 8, MH, and MHS; c) Elements of LGG and LGG-MHS as mapped using TEM [139]. Copyright

1 2022. Adapted from Springer Nature. (III) Glioblastoma treatment with brain-targeted
2 CRISPR/Cas9 nanomedicine [140]. Copyright 2022. Reproduced with permission from
3 Elsevier.

4 5 *7.3. Magnetic resonance imaging of nanomaterials loaded with CRISPR/Cas9 components for* 6 *cancer therapy*

7 The integration of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) with CRISPR/Cas9 gene-editing
8 technology is emerging as a cutting-edge strategy for cancer diagnosis and therapy [142]. MRI
9 is a non-invasive imaging technology renowned for its high spatial resolution, deep tissue
10 penetration, and outstanding soft tissue contrast. In conjunction with CRISPR/Cas9, MRI
11 enables longitudinal monitoring of tumor growth and therapeutic response, in addition to
12 assisting in the tracking of gene-editing component delivery and biodistribution [10]. It is very
13 difficult to precisely distribute the gene-editing machinery to tumor locations within the
14 framework of CRISPR/Cas9-mediated cancer treatment [143]. To tackle this, researchers are
15 working on MRI-visible nanocarriers that can encapsulate and transport CRISPR components
16 like plasmid DNA, messenger RNA, or RNP complexes, all while carrying MRI contrast agents
17 like SPIONs or gadolinium-based agents. Therapeutic genome editing and diagnostic imaging
18 are both made possible by these multifunctional nanocarriers. In addition, external magnetic
19 fields can be used to guide magnetically responsive carriers to certain tumor areas during MRI-
20 guided CRISPR administration, which improves localization and decreases off-target effects
21 [144]. Using these magnetically guided nanoscale systems, which offer constant image
22 feedback, greatly improves the accuracy of gene-editing treatments. To further expand its
23 involvement in therapy assessment, MRI can help visualize changes in the tumor
24 microenvironment after CRISPR editing, such as altered vascularization, necrosis, or immune
25 cell infiltration.

26 Liu et al. constructed a unique self-assembled manganese sulphide nanourchin using
27 CRISPR/Cas9 and hybrid MCRT [145]. Nanourchins' unique shape and cationic surface make
28 them ideal for encapsulating erythrocyte-tumor cell hybrid membranes and loading large-scale
29 CRISPR/Cas9 enzymes, resulting in a nano platform with extended circulation and pinpoint
30 tumour targeting. MCRT that responds to changes in pH can release CRISPR/Cas9 into an
31 acidic tumour microenvironment after decomposing into H₂S and Mn²⁺. H₂S is able to
32 promote Mn²⁺ self-enhanced chemodynamic treatment (CDT) by up-regulating intracellular
33 hydrogen peroxide levels through catalase inhibition [145]. Furthermore, H₂S has the potential
34 to work in tandem with the released CRISPR/Cas9 to achieve self-enhanced gene therapy by

1 downregulating the level of intracellular anti-apoptotic protein surviving. The augmentation of
 2 tumour contrast on magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is also significantly better when MCRT
 3 is administered systemically. Crucially, both immunogenic cell death and a strong anti-tumor
 4 immune response are induced simultaneously by H₂S-enhanced CDT-gene therapy as
 5 demonstrated in **Fig. 11** [145].

6
 7 **Fig. 11.** (I) Diagrammatic representation of the synthesis and action mechanism of multi-
 8 targeted MR imaging and self-enhanced chemodynamic gene immunotherapy for tumours. (II)

1 Coronal and axial T1-weighted MRI scans of mice taken at various intervals after MCR and
2 hybrid membrane encapsulation (MCRT) injection; white dashed circles indicate tumour sites
3 [145]. Copyright 2024. Reproduced with permission from John Wiley & Sons.

4 5 *7.4. Bioluminescence Imaging of nanomaterials loaded with CRISPR/Cas9 components for* 6 *cancer therapy*

7 A non-invasive optical imaging method known as bioluminescence imaging (BLI) is
8 extensively utilised in preclinical research for real-time monitoring of biological processes
9 [146]. A luciferase enzyme (often firefly luciferase) and its substrate such
10 as luciferin enzymatically react to create light, which is the key component. Researchers may
11 see and measure cellular and molecular processes in real time by capturing the emitted light
12 using a sensitive charge-coupled device (CCD) camera. Among the many benefits of BLI is
13 that it eliminates the need for dissection while longitudinally monitoring gene expression,
14 tumour growth, infection dissemination, or therapy response in the same individual [147]. By
15 genetically engineering tumour cells to express luciferase, this approach enables the
16 visualisation of tumour development and metastasis, making it very relevant in cancer research.
17 Bioluminescence is superior to fluorescence imaging for deep-tissue applications due to its
18 high signal-to-noise ratio and the fact that mammalian tissues do not generate background
19 luminescence [148]. Also, with various luciferase-enzyme-substrate systems, BLI enables multiplex
20 imaging, which allows for the simultaneous monitoring of many biological activities.
21 Bioluminescence imaging is still a potent technique for in vivo cellular and molecular imaging,
22 even if it has lower spatial resolution than MRI or CT.

23 Feng et al. showed that nanoparticles responsive to near-infrared (NIR) and reducing agents
24 could control the release of CRISPR-Cas9 RNP and codelivery with the anticancer
25 photosensitizer chlorin e6 (Ce6) [149]. The His-tagged Cas9 RNP can be bound by micelles
26 coated with nitrotriacetic acid. The release of nanoparticles from tumour cells was set in
27 motion by Ce6's production of ROS in response to NIR. A disulphide bond reduction allowed
28 the cytoplasmic release of Cas9/sgRNA. The antioxidant regulator Nrf2 was enhanced in
29 tumour cells' sensitivity to ROS by Cas9/sgRNA targeting [149]. Cas9 degradation in
30 lysosomes and gene editing failure in normal tissues occurred in the absence of NIR irradiation.
31 In vivo evidence supported the idea that Nrf2 gene editing and Ce6 photodynamic treatment
32 work synergistically. Combining stimuli-responsive nanoparticles with controlled release of
33 CRISPR-Cas9 RNP and codelivery with Ce6 offers a flexible approach to gene editing that
34 may have synergistic medicinal effects (**Fig. S6 (I)**) [149]. Rosenblum et al. utilised amino-

1 ionizable lipid for Cas9 mRNA and sgRNAs delivery [150]. In aggressive orthotopic
2 glioblastoma, a single intracerebral injection of sgPLK1-cLNPs allowed for around 70% gene
3 editing in vivo, leading to tumour cell apoptosis, 50% tumour growth inhibition, and 30%
4 increased survival [150]. Moreover, authors also modified cLNPs for antibody-targeted
5 delivery so that they could reach tumours that had spread. The selective uptake of EGFR-
6 targeted sgPLK1-cLNPs into disseminated ovarian tumours, up to approximately 80% gene
7 editing in vivo, inhibition of tumour growth, and an 80% increase in survival were all outcomes
8 of intraperitoneal injections of these nanoparticles (Fig. S6 (II)) [150].

9 10 **8. Challenges and Future Prospects**

11 Genome editing using CRISPR/Cas9 has allowed for precise programmable changes to
12 DNA, which has greatly impacted scientific research. The integration with nanotechnology has
13 led to the development of theranostic drug delivery systems, which combine therapeutic and
14 diagnostic capabilities. These state-of-the-art systems use imaging techniques including
15 photoacoustic imaging, confocal, bioluminescence, near-infrared (NIR), or fluorescence to
16 simultaneously alter genes and assess the treatment efficacy in real-time. Although
17 CRISPR/Cas9 theranostic systems show promise, there are still many obstacles that prevent
18 their full clinical translation. A significant hurdle for therapeutic applications is the packaging
19 of CRISPR components into a single vector. Whether it's gene, RNA, or protein-based delivery,
20 the packaging challenge is there. This is particularly evident in gene-based delivery using
21 adeno-associated virus (AAV), which has a packaging limit of approximately 4.7 kilo basepairs
22 (kb). Given that SpCas9 genes are about 3 kb, incorporating extra genes, spare oligonucleotides,
23 or sgRNA into single AAV vector-based CRISPR gene delivery applications become
24 challenging. As a workaround, researchers have shown Cas9 divided into two AAV vectors
25 (SaCas9) or smaller Cas9 (SaCas9), but how well these tools work for genome editing is still
26 up for debate. Although appealing, there are additional obstacles to protein-based CRISPR
27 delivery. For example, sgRNA is negatively charged with approximately 100 PO³⁻ groups, and
28 SpCas9 is a big protein with a net positive surface charge, measuring 160 kDa and having a
29 hydrodynamic diameter of about 7.5 nm. As a result, developing delivery vehicles that can
30 package these elements using supramolecular chemistry can be quite challenging. Additionally,
31 the vector design could be further complicated if extra spare DNA (size in kbp) is incorporated
32 for numerous uses. The potential for off-target effects is a big drawback of CRISPR-based
33 genome editing. Although the sgRNA is engineered to target a particular gene, it is not
34 uncommon for the same Cas9/sgRNA to target a large number of nonspecific genes. Constant

1 Cas9/sgRNA expression over an extended period of time is a major issue with gene-based
2 CRISPR delivery since it increases the likelihood of off-target effects caused by repeated
3 exposure to nonspecific genes. To lessen the off-target effect, researchers have developed a
4 variety of approaches, such as creating a highly selective Cas9 protein. Nevertheless, the off-
5 target impacts of these systems in living organisms have not been thoroughly investigated. To
6 counter this, protein-based CRISPR delivery allows for brief contact with the host genome and
7 the Cas9/sgRNA, which could lead to fewer off-target events.

8 Utilising CRISPR/Cas9 systems through in vitro laboratory engineering has numerous
9 advantages. It will be necessary to resolve numerous issues before the full promise of
10 CRISPR/Cas9 techniques can be realised. The system itself still has issues with off-target
11 cutting. Although they are not a perfect solution, this problem has been addressed through the
12 engineering of Cas9 nickases and mutations that increase its specific DNA binding. While
13 numerous prediction software sgRNA design tools have been developed and a great deal of
14 effort has gone into researching sgRNA binding and off-target tolerance, our knowledge of off-
15 target consequences is still limited. For CRISPR/Cas9 to live up to its potential, this is an
16 essential area that needs more research. An all-purpose delivery technique has not yet emerged,
17 and gene cargo delivery systems continue to be the biggest challenge for CRISPR/Cas9
18 applications. Alternatively, there are a number of ways that CRISPR can be delivered to cells.
19 Every delivery method has its pros and cons. Some methods are more suitable for specific types
20 of delivery than others; for example, some are more specialised to cells in a flask than to living
21 organisms. Even more so, ribonucleoprotein delivery, rather than plasmid DNA or messenger
22 RNA, typically yields the finest gene editing results with little off-target consequences. The
23 transport of small molecule cargo is now more flexible than that of the relatively big protein-
24 nucleic acid conjugation. The field stands to benefit greatly from the creation of novel delivery
25 methods that facilitate efficient RNP distribution. Verifying the selected system's safety and
26 specificity is yet another hurdle for delivery systems. Concern for the safety of living creatures
27 is constant; a delivery vehicle with high-specificity targeting of the target cells would reduce
28 off-target effects and increase safety. It is also critical to do long-term safety assessments on
29 the components, particularly for nanoparticle carriers. Natural, biocompatible, and able to
30 traverse biological barriers, EVs have now come to light as potential nanocarriers for
31 CRISPR/Cas9 delivery. Nevertheless, there are still significant technological challenges in
32 producing, purifying, and efficiently loading with CRISPR cargos on a large scale. Therapeutic
33 results can vary due to the absence of standardised protocols. Also, there are regulatory hurdles
34 with modified EVs that need to be overcome with thorough preclinical and clinical studies.

1 When it comes to regulations, organizations like the FDA consider CRISPR/Cas9 products
2 to be biologics. As a result, these products must undergo rigorous preclinical and clinical
3 testing, as well as an Investigational New Drug (IND) application, before they can be approved.
4 In human trials, regulatory frameworks aim to evaluate efficacy, safety (including immune
5 responses and off-target effects), and ethical acceptability. Unresolved ethical and safety
6 concerns have led several states to ban or severely restrict heritable germline editing, in contrast
7 to the carefully supervised clinical pathways for somatic CRISPR medicines. Protecting trial
8 participants, ensuring comprehensive risk/benefit analysis, and preventing premature or
9 unethical uses of gene-editing technologies all depend on a regulatory system that is both
10 rigorous and transparent. Balancing innovation with ethical responsibility requires
11 interdisciplinary dialogue among scientists, ethicists, policymakers, and the public. While
12 CRISPR/Cas9 offers promising avenues to treat genetic disorders, establishing comprehensive
13 ethical frameworks, enforcing strict regulatory oversight, promoting equitable access, and
14 transparently addressing technical failures like off-target effects are essential to its responsible
15 clinical translation.

16 At the same time, there has been a lot of success in using CRISPR-based systems for cancer
17 diagnostics, especially in the area of biomarker sensing. Coupling CRISPR-loaded nanocarriers
18 with advanced imaging modalities allows for the monitoring of biodistribution and gene-
19 editing efficiency by photoacoustic fluorescence, or magnetic resonance imaging. However,
20 there is still a need for improvement in the sensitivity, resolution, and interoperability of these
21 integrated theranostic systems with current clinical imaging platforms. Comprehensive safety
22 and toxicology assessments of nanomaterials employed for CRISPR delivery are also required.
23 For nanocarriers to be clinically viable, extensive research on their immunogenicity, long-term
24 biodistribution, degradation mechanisms, and possible accumulation in non-target organs is
25 required. Key issues that require additional exploration include systemic circulation, repeated
26 administration, and possible involvement with the immune system. The creation of
27 multifunctional, stimuli-responsive nanocarriers capable of controlled and targeted delivery of
28 gene-editing tools is the key to the future of CRISPR/Cas9-based cancer therapies. Improving
29 the spatial and temporal precision of gene editing is possible with smart nanocarriers that can
30 respond to both internal (pH, redox, enzyme levels) and exterior (ultrasound, magnetic fields)
31 stimuli. To further enhance targeting efficiency and decrease off-target effects, tumor-targeted
32 ligands or cell-penetrating peptides could be integrated. Furthermore, there is great promise in
33 the merging of CRISPR diagnostics with personalised cancer treatment. Personalised gene-
34 editing treatments may become a reality if patient-specific biomarkers have been identified and

1 CRISPR technologies have been developed to accommodate particular tumour genotypes.
2 There may be synergistic effects and improved therapeutic efficacy when CRISPR is combined
3 with current methods like immunotherapy, chemotherapy, or epigenetic modulators. Crucially,
4 imaging agents that are co-delivered with gene editing tools will allow for real-time imaging
5 of editing events, which will be useful for tracking therapeutic response and fine-tuning dosage
6 plans. Scalable production processes and regulatory frameworks for CRISPR-loaded
7 nanocarriers are essential for enabling clinical translation. Improving design parameters,
8 anticipating off-target consequences, and optimising therapy could be made easier with the use
9 of artificial intelligence and machine learning technologies. For the sake of patients, it is
10 essential to prioritise standardised toxicological evaluations and long-term safety studies.

11 12 **9. Conclusion**

13 Since its adoption in 2013, CRISPR/Cas9 has changed the face of gene editing owing to its
14 simplicity, adaptability, and naive nature, this gene-editing tool has become an essential
15 component of cancer research and has found its way into the present system of cancer
16 management. Gene engineering has created a new age in cancer research by shedding light on
17 the function of many signalling molecules, which in turn has facilitated the development of
18 cutting-edge cancer treatments. The CRISPR/Cas9 platform has emerged as a leading light in
19 the fight against cancer by providing innovative strategies and detailed plans for targeted gene
20 and immunotherapy. A persistent challenge in gene and drug therapy is the lack of rapid and
21 site-specific medicine delivery of therapeutic agents. The precision and adaptability of
22 biomarker detection techniques have been greatly improved with the integration of CRISPR/Cas9
23 technology into cancer diagnostics and therapies. This study summarises the new possibilities
24 for CRISPR/Cas9 systems to detect cancer biomarkers such as resistance-associated genomic
25 changes, circulating tumour DNA (ctDNA), and DNA mutations in a quick, sensitive, and
26 specific manner. For early diagnosis, classification of patients, and real-time monitoring of
27 therapy efficacy, these qualities are crucial. Novel nanoscale delivery technologies, including
28 tailored nanoformulations and EV-mediated transport, have greatly enhanced the stability,
29 targeting efficiency, and therapeutic output of platforms based on CRISPR/Cas9. However,
30 because of advancements in nanotechnology, CRISPR delivery has entered a new neo-
31 bioengineering stage. The standard technique of delivering CRISPR/Cas9 has its limitations,
32 hence new approaches are being developed to circumvent these issues. Research into site-
33 specific delivery, controlled release, bio-distribution, and the fate of CRISPR/Cas9
34 nanoformulations after administration will reap the benefits of CRISPR delivery system

1 development in this regard. Among new approaches, theranostic nanoplateforms are
2 revolutionary because they combine diagnostic imaging with gene editing-based treatments.
3 These systems allow for the regulated release of CRISPR components and tumor-specific
4 delivery, and they also allow for the monitoring of biodistribution and therapy response in real-
5 time. With these skills, treatment precision can be greatly improved, systemic toxicity can be
6 reduced, and timely therapeutic interventions can be made possible. Improving encapsulation
7 efficiency, ensuring cargo stability, minimising off-target impacts, and attaining industrial
8 scalability with minimum variability are significant challenges that still need to be addressed
9 despite recent achievements. The immune system's interactions with CRISPR-loaded
10 nanocarriers and their long-term biological fate should also be the subject of future research.

11 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

13 **Aseem Setia:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing
14 – review & editing. **Dipali Patil:** Writing review and editing, Data curation, Formal analysis,
15 **Nandini Vinodrao Randhave:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation.
16 **Vaishali:** Writing – review & editing. **Nidhi Verma:** Writing – review & editing. **Komal Rani:**
17 Writing – review & editing. **Akshay Kale:** Formal analysis, data curation. **Bhima Wagh:**
18 Formal analysis, Visualization. **Vikas Kumar:** Visualization, Validation. **Ankit Kumar**
19 **Malik:** Visualization, Validation. **Arjun Kumar Popu J:** Writing review and editing, Data
20 curation. **Kalim Deshmukh:** Writing review and editing, Data curation, Formal analysis,
21 Funding acquisition, Resources, Project administration. **Madaswamy S. Muthu:** Writing –
22 review & editing, Subject administration, Supervision, Conceptualization, Investigation,
23 Methodology.

24 **Declaration of competing interest**

26 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
27 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

28 **Data Availability Statement:**

29 The preprint copy of this article is available at:
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